

ASSESSMENT TECHNIQUES FOR SUSTAINING STUDENTS' INTEREST IN THE LEARNING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

BY

IJOKO GREGORY AGU, Ph.D

Department of Foundations, Arts and Social Science Education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State
E-mail Address: ijokogregory15agu@gmail.com / ijokoag@fuotuo.ke.edu.ng. Mobile No: 08134925263, 07040187032
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Abstract

This study investigated assessment techniques for sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language in Junior Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was comprised of all the 21,616 junior secondary schools (JSS 3) students and 450 English Language Teachers in the 319 public junior secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The sample size for the study was 393 which consisted of 343 public junior secondary school (III) students and 50 English language teachers. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to select the sample while purposive sampling technique was used to select the 50 schools. The instrument for the collection of data for this study was a questionnaire developed by the researchers, titled "Assessment Techniques for Sustaining Students' Interest in the Learning of English Language Questionnaire" (ATSSILELQ) made up of 20 items. The Cronbach alpha method was adopted to determine the reliability coefficient of 0.86. Data collected were subjected to mean and standard deviation which were used to analysis the research question while t- test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the findings, the study concluded that teachers in junior secondary schools used the traditional assessment techniques, less use of maiden-device systems and technology assessment techniques to sustain students' interest in the teaching and learning of English language. Therefore, the researchers recommended that teachers in junior secondary schools should use a variety of assessment techniques especially modern media driven systems and technologies to sustain learners' interest in English language

Key words: Assessment; English Language; Interest; Learning; Learning Technique

Introduction

Language is one of those characteristics that set man apart from all other living creatures. It is the vehicle of social interaction. Man needs effective language to function properly in the work place, places of workshop for social interaction and indeed for functional literacy. Onuigbo (2016) posited that, English language is the most enduring colonial heritage and one that has far-reaching effect in the socio-political and educational life of Nigerians. According to Onuigbo (2016), the language has remained a strong unifying factor and in fact the only compromise language among the various ethnic groups in Nigeria. It has become the language of

trade, documentation, literature, mass media, governance and skill acquisition.

The English language has long been conferred with the status of a second language (L₂) in Nigeria. Being a second language means that for most people in Nigeria, the next language of proficiency after the mother tongue which the first language L₁ is the English language. Ogbuehi as cited in Ugboja and Ijoko (2022) stated that, language is an instrument of socialisation for all members of a community. The acquisition of the vocal symbols of a language is a pre-requisite to an individual's full integration and participation as a member of that community. In Nigeria, English has attained remarkable heights in terms of its use and role in

the nation's development and interaction across the six geo-political zones in the country. Akabogu (2018) opined that, English language exerts a lot of influence on the political, cultural, socio-linguistic and educational aspects of the people's life. This is because the English language is used for various purposes.

The vital role of English in the school curriculum also confers on it prestige, which no other language commands in Nigeria (Bamgbose as cited in Ijoko et al., 2022). According to Akabogu (2018), this prestige is further strengthened by the fact that one is not deemed to have passed the school certificate examinations without a pass in English. As one of the legacies from the British colonialists, it has come to stay as a major machine of communication among different language groups and almost all life transactions of the Nigerian people. It is therefore necessary for the educational system to maintain a standard of English which should be near to that of native speakers of the language. Currently, in Nigeria, criticisms run high against what people call deteriorating level of performance in English language in schools generally. The public's ready basis for measuring these standards whatever they are, is the present school children's ability to write, speak and comprehend, simple and correct English.

English language has come to stay in Nigeria because of the diverse roles it plays in communication. A credit pass in English language is still a prerequisite for admission into higher institutions of learning and for employment in various offices. According to the National Policy on Education (2013), English language is the major medium of instruction in secondary schools, hence the pride of the teaching and learning occupies in the nation's education system. Yet, there is the hue and cry that the standard of proficiency in the language

has fallen to a regrettable level in both internal and external examinations (Ijoko et al., 2024). Efforts are being made by ministries of education throughout the country to find solution to the situation in which a student who has completed secondary school education is unable to write a good letter or essay.

Interest is an important variable in language learning because when one is interested in a language, one becomes eager to learn it. Interest is a persisting inclination to be attentive and enjoy some activities. Interest has been viewed as an emotionally oriented behavioural trait which determines a learner's urge and vigour to tackle educational programmes or other activities (Chukwu, 2012). Interest is useful in predicting the success and the satisfaction which an individual is likely to obtain from engaging in certain activities now and in future. It is for teachers to be acquainted with adequate teaching assessment techniques and materials which will increase students' interest in language learning, especially English language. It is therefore necessary to explore assessment techniques that will sustain students' interest in the learning of English language in junior secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Assessment techniques are the special strategies employed by teachers to sustain the interest of the students in the learning of English language. A technique is also a very specific concrete step designed to accomplish an immediate objective. Marily et al. (2021) pointed out that assessment techniques are the means to attain the end. In order for approach to be translated into a method, and a method into techniques, in instructional system must be designed in line with the objectives of the learning which would determine the content to be selected and organized, the type of tasks to be performed, the roles of the students and the roles of the teachers. A technique may be associated with more than one skill; a technique is therefore implementational, that which actually takes

place in the classroom. It is a particular contrivance, used to accomplish an immediate objective.

Assessment techniques are embedded in instructional methods. According to Casey (2018), a method is a set of materials organized into a fixed pedagogic sequence, requiring the use of classroom techniques which embody a certain view of language learning. Assessment can be seen as the end, while the techniques are the means to attain the end. It then means that techniques are subsets of method. Some examples of the techniques used in the teaching and learning of English studies are: group activity, questionnaire, role playing, dialogue, minimal pairs, dictionary, structural drills, project work, homework, conversation gap-filling exercise, questions and answers and personal interaction. Group activity is essential for practice in communication. There is no limit to the topic that can be discussed among groups or between pairs of students. The food they like, the games they play, clothes that are in fashion, motor cars, famous people in all walk of life, the kind of jobs their parents do. There are also a number of activities to choose from, such as word games and puzzles, finding directions in a map and drawing up rules and regulations for a club.

Similarly, there are other modern media used for assessment techniques. Such modern media include audio and video tapes, language laboratory, programmes text, folk tale, recorded tapes and disc of RP account, magazines and newspapers, radio and television programmes. The radio, for instance, is a form of electronic media that appeals to the sense of hearing and it is the most popular and most common type of mass media. There are special broadcasting units responsible in most countries for the programmes produced for schools. These units

work hard to make up their programmes match the needs of students.

The need and value of assessment techniques in teaching and learning of English language cannot be over emphasised. Adeniyi (2016) noted that, these techniques or teaching aids of various types are of tremendous importance in the teaching of language at any level, especially at the junior secondary school. They easily arouse interest, and provide motivation. They help to make learning meaningful by relating language function to more concrete objects and situations.

There is still a raging controversy on whether gender has a significant influence on students' performance in English language (Offorma, 2004). Ijoko (2021) conducted a study on students' performance in Oral English using project- based and group discussion learning techniques in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The study found out that, female students performed better than boys. Ching (2021) studied the academic achievement of secondary school students in relation to gender and the results revealed that significant gender differences existed in academic performance of students. The author disclosed that females showed a higher reading ability and academic achievement than males. Greef (2023) conducted a study that analyse the relationship between academic achievement and intelligence of boys and girls. Findings showed that, there was a correlation between academic achievement and intelligence of the students and the correlation was greater in case of girls than boys. Therefore, the present researchers attempted to find the extent to which students (boys and girls) interest in sustained in the learning of English language and the type of assessment techniques teachers employ to sustain students' interest in the learning of English language in junior secondary schools.

Statement of the Problem

Students' poor performance in English language is often blamed on teachers especially when some students obtain credit and distinction passes in other subjects but fail in English language, despite the established strong relationship between proficiency in English language and success in academic work. There is still a high failure rate in students' performance in English at the secondary level in many of the public examinations which is due to the fact that, the students' interest is not being adequately aroused and sustained for the learning of the language. The study seeks to investigate the assessment techniques teacher employ to sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language in Junior Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The broad purpose of this study is to investigate assessment techniques for sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language in Junior Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the extent students are interested in the learning of English language.
2. examine the assessment techniques that teachers use in sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language.

Research Questions

Two research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. To what extent are students interested in the learning of the English language?
2. What are the assessment techniques teachers use in sustaining students' interest in the learning of the English language?

Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses guided the study at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁. There is no significant difference between male and female students' interest in the learning of English language.

H₀₂. There is no significant difference between the assessment techniques used by male and female teachers in sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was comprised of all the 21,616 junior secondary three (JS III) students with 450 English language teachers in the 319 public junior secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The sample for the study was determined to be 393 using Taro Yamen's formular. Meanwhile 50 public junior secondary schools were chosen purposively. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select 343 and 50 junior secondary THREE (JS III) students and English language teachers respectively. Furthermore, a simple random sampling technique was used to choose the students while all the 50 English Language teachers were enumerated and used for the study. The instrument for the collection of data for this study was a questionnaire developed by the researchers and, it is titled "Assessment Techniques for Sustaining Students' Interest in the Learning of English Language Questionnaire" (ATSSILELQ) made up of 20 items. The Cronbach alpha method was adopted to determine the reliability of the instrument. The instrument ATSSILELQ was given to a group of twenty (20) junior secondary school students who were not part of the sample size and the reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained. Data analysis was subjected to mean and standard deviation which were used to answered research question while the t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance.

Results

Research question one: To what extent are students interested in learning English language?

Table 1: Response on English language interest inventory (ELII)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std	Remark
1.	I like to study English language at school	3.80	0.95	Agreed
2.	I always pay attention when English language is taught in the class	3.75	0.91	Agreed
3.	I do not like to attend English language classes	3.37	0.84	Agreed
4.	I fail to concentrate when English language is taught	3.30	0.82	Agreed
5.	I do not exchange English Language notes	3.79	0.94	Agreed
6.	I do not like completing English language assignment	3.79	0.94	Agreed
7.	I always find something else to do instead of studying English language	3.53	0.87	Agreed
8.	I am unhappy when I write assignment on English Language	3.53	0.86	Agreed
9.	I do not like to buy English language textbooks	3.57	0.87	Agreed
10.	I do not like speaking English language	3.45	0.85	Agreed
Grand Mean/SD		3.59	0.89	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

*mean >2.50= “Agree”, mean<2.50= “Disagree”

The data in Table 1 showed that items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 are above the cut off mark of 2.50. However, the computation of data in items 1-10 of the questionnaire in Table 1 revealed that the students have a grand mean/SD of 3.59±0.89. Therefore, it means that there is a strong indication that the students in junior secondary

schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria have a high extent of interest in learning English language.

Research Question Two: What assessment techniques do teachers used to sustain students’ interest in the teaching and learning of English language in junior secondary schools?

Table 2: Techniques used by teachers to sustain students’ interest in the teaching and learning of English language.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std	Remark
1.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if picture and illustrations are used in teaching the subject	3.24	0.94	Agreed
2.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if folktale and stories are used in teaching the subject	2.06	0.86	Disagreed
3.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if it is taught in a language laboratory	3.13	0.91	Agreed
4.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if radio broadcast instruction is used	3.04	0.90	Agreed
5.	I will be interesting in English language class if computer programmes are used	2.65	0.89	Agreed
6.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if tape recorder sounds are played in the class	2.65	0.89	Agreed
7.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if groups activity and role play are used in teaching	3.06	0.91	Agreed
8.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if I exchanges notes with students from other neighboring school	2.13	0.87	Disagreed
9.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if spelling and pronunciation are taught through dictation	3.37	0.95	Agreed
10.	I will be interesting in English language lesson if recitation is used in teaching the subject	2.02	0.86	Disagreed
Grand Mean/SD		2.74	0.90	Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

*mean >2.50= “Agree”, mean<2.50= “Disagree”

The data in table 2 showed that items 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 9 are above the cut off mark of 2.50. On the other hand, items 2, 8 and 10 are below the cut off mark of 2.50. However, the computation of data in items 1-10 of the questionnaire revealed that the students have a grand mean/SD

of 2.74±0.90. Therefore, there is an indication that assessment techniques used by teachers do not marginally sustain students’ interest in the teaching and learning of English language in Junior Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female students’ interest in the learning of English language.

Table 3: t-Test Analysis of Male and Female Students’ Interested in the Learning of English Language

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	P-value	t-cal	t-cri	Remark
Male	161	2.50	1.04	341	0.574	0.563	1.96	Ho retained
Female	182	2.56	1.09					

* $P > 0.05$ Not significant at the 0.05 level

Table 3 showed that, with the degree of freedom 198 at 0.05 level of significance, the t-calculated value of 0.563 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 and p-value of 0.574 greater than 0.05.

Hence the null hypothesis is retained. This indicated that there is no significant difference between the extent of male and female students’ interest in the learning of English language in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the assessment techniques used by male and female teachers in sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language.

Table 4.7: t-Test Analysis of the Assessment Techniques used by Male and Female Teachers in Sustaining Students' Interest in the Learning of English Language.

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	P-value	t-cal	t-cri	Remark
Male	26	2.75	0.46	48	0.8224	0.2247	1.96	Ho retained
Female	24	2.76	0.43					

* $P > 0.05$ Not significant at the 0.05 level

Table 4. showed that, with the degree of freedom 48 at 0.05 level of significance, the t-calculated value of 0.2247 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 and p-value of 0.8224 is greater than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is retained. This indicated that, there is no significant difference in the assessment techniques used by male and female teachers in sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language.

The purpose of this study is to investigate assessment techniques for sustaining students' interest in the learning of English language in Junior Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. From the finding in Table 1, it is clear that the students are interested in learning English language; this is because the students’ responses to the English language interest inventory are above the cut of mark of 2.50. All the evidence in Table 2 indicated that, the teachers assessment

Discussions

techniques such as modern media such which include audio and video tapes, language laboratory, recorded tapes and disc of RP account, magazines and newspapers, radio programmers, television programmers and computer programmes are of interest to the learners but the teachers are used to the traditional assessment techniques in the teaching of English language such as programmes text like folk tale, and recitation. This finding agreed with the research finding of Obasi and Ilo (2023) who observed that, techniques used by teachers in teaching English language in secondary are inappropriate in many respects. They, therefore, recommended that, teachers should adopt the current assessment techniques in content delivery.

Conclusion

The teachers in junior secondary schools used the traditional assessment techniques, that is, the common techniques that is popular among the English language teachers like group activity, dialogues, dictionary, dictation, homework, discussion, textbooks and real objects to teach. They do not use modern media driven system and technology to sustain students' interest in the teaching and learning of English language. These are radio broadcast instructions, recorded tapes and disc of RP account. Therefore, teachers of English language are encouraged to adopt current assessment techniques such as broadcast instruction, tape sounds, cartoons, and puzzles, glossary of words and phrases from passages television programmes, film trips and projectors and language laboratory in content delivery.

Recommendations

Based on the finding and educational implications of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers in junior secondary schools should use variety of techniques

especially modern media driven system and technologies to sustain their interest in English language.

2. Teacher in junior secondary schools should assume new roles and use new technologies support instructional tools, they should be familiar with variety of assessment techniques in delivery methods rather than relying on textbooks, chalkboard and lecture method. With the application of modern technologies in classroom, instruction can be more students centered individualized.
3. Seminars, workshops and in-service training are also recommended for the teachers to up-date and up-grade their knowledge.

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